

Deep learning models for estimating volume and Lorey's height across Nordic countries using optical and SAR satellite images

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Highlights

- A large-scale, fine-resolution forest resource map was produced in Norway from multisource optical and SAR imagery, trained on an ALS-based reference map using a UNet deep learning framework.
- The best UNet model achieved coefficients of determination (R^2) of 0.63 and 0.55 for timber volume and Lorey's height, respectively, compared to 0.39 and 0.37 from the reference approach (k-nearest neighbours with $k = 7$).
- We also analyse the geographical transferability of the pre-trained model on Finnish data to fine-tune for Norwegian conditions.

Abstract

Spatially explicit information on forest resources and structure is essential for sustainable forest management and evidence-based policy-making. In the Nordic region, large-scale forest mapping often relies on integrating National Forest Inventory (NFI) field plots with airborne laser scanning (ALS) data. However, the infrequent coverage of nationwide ALS campaigns limits their use for continuous monitoring. Satellite imagery, with its high temporal and spatial resolution, provides a promising alternative. We evaluate UNet-based deep learning models trained on wall-to-wall ALS-derived forest resource maps for predicting volume and Lorey's height in Norway using optical (Sentinel-2) and SAR (Sentinel-1, PALSAR-2) data. The UNet models, trained on both Finnish and Norwegian ALS maps, are benchmarked against kNN models based on Norwegian NFI data. Transfer learning is further explored by fine-tuning models using Norwegian NFI plots. Model uncertainties are assessed using 541 reserved NFI plots and 44 independent validation stands mainly including high-volume boreal forests ($>200 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$). The best-performing UNet model, trained on Norwegian ALS data, achieved an R^2 of 0.63 for volume and 0.55 for Lorey's height, consistently outperforming kNN. Fine-tuning improved model transferability, with gains in R^2 of up to 0.13 for volume and 0.46 for Lorey's height, when adapting the Finnish model to Norwegian conditions. Utilizing SAR data alongside optical data enhanced model accuracy, with R^2 improvement ranging from 0.03 to 0.19. Overall, our findings demonstrate the potential of UNet models trained on wall-to-wall ALS maps, offering a transferable approach for forest resource mapping across Nordic countries.

Keywords: UNet, deep learning, forest resource mapping, satellite imagery, SAR, multisource

40 1. Introduction

41 Quantifying the status and trends of forest resources and structure—such as timber volume and Lorey’s
42 height—is crucial for informing evidence-based policy and management decisions across local,
43 national, and international levels (Tomppo et al., 2010; Vidal et al., 2016a). Sampling-based National
44 Forest Inventories (NFIs) provide this information at national and regional scales, forming the
45 foundation for strategic decision and policy-making regarding key ecosystem services, including
46 bioenergy potential, biodiversity, and changes in carbon stock (Vidal et al., 2016b; Breidenbach et al.,
47 2020). However, because NFIs are sampling-based surveys, their capacity to produce reliable estimates
48 at local scales is restricted (Breidenbach and Astrup, 2012; Astrup et al., 2019). To bridge this gap, NFI
49 field plots are often combined with remotely sensed data to model relationships between field-
50 observed forest attributes and remote sensing-based predictor variables, enabling mapping between
51 NFI plot locations (McRoberts and Tomppo, 2007; Kangas et al., 2018). This approach aligns with the
52 requirements of several international policy frameworks—including the EU Forest Strategy for 2030,
53 the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and the EU Deforestation Regulation—which emphasize the need for
54 spatially explicit forest monitoring at both national and local scales. Consequently, integrating remotely
55 sensed data has become essential for producing detailed forest resource maps and information.

56 Some of the earliest national forest maps were based on a combination of NFI and Landsat data
57 (Gjertsen, 2007; McRoberts and Tomppo, 2007). In many countries, national forest resource maps are
58 today based on integrating field plots from NFIs with country-wide Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) data
59 (Kangas et al., 2018). ALS offers detailed 3D information on forest structure, enabling accurate
60 estimation of key attributes such as timber volume and Lorey’s height. However, national ALS
61 campaigns lack the temporal frequency needed for effective forest monitoring. For example, Norway’s
62 nationwide ALS campaign required approximately ten years to complete full coverage (Hauglin et al.,
63 2021), compared to a seven-year timeframe in Sweden (Nilsson et al., 2017). In Finland, the future ALS
64 campaigns are planned to be conducted in nine-year cycles (NLS, 2025). In contrast, Earth Observation
65 (EO) datasets—such as optical imagery from Sentinel-2 and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data from
66 Sentinel-1 or ALOS-2 PALSAR-2—offer both high temporal and spatial coverage. Several studies have
67 utilized optical remote sensing for forest resource mapping, such as Sentinel-2 or LANDSAT (Astola et
68 al., 2019; Lang et al., 2019; Miettinen et al., 2021) or have combined EO with ALS data (Esteban et al.,
69 2019; Astola et al., 2021). SAR data with clear sensitivity to forest structure have also been used for
70 forest mapping, primarily at stand-level or coarser mapping units and in wide-area studies (Santoro et
71 al., 2011; Antropov et al., 2017; Ge et al., 2023b). Recent studies have shown that the combination of
72 optical and SAR data improves the quantification of forest structural characteristics (Wittke et al., 2019;
73 Persson et al., 2021; Ge et al., 2022, 2023a), especially if SAR operates in lower frequencies (e.g., L-
74 band used on board ALOS-2), which opens new possibilities for improving the accuracy of maps for
75 estimating forest attributes.

76 EO-based forest resource maps have been created using statistical methods such as linear regression,
77 k-nearest neighbours (kNN), and ensemble-based machine learning techniques such as random forests.
78 Studies using only Sentinel-2 data with these approaches have reported RMSEs ranging from 27.2% to
79 59.3% for estimates of volume and Lorey’s height in boreal forest contexts (Astola et al., 2019;
80 Miettinen et al., 2021; Persson et al., 2021). When using SAR data alone, RMSEs for volume range from
81 32% to 54.3% (Wittke et al., 2019; Ge et al., 2023b; Persson et al., 2021). One study systematically
82 tested the integration of optical and SAR datasets using kNN method and reported improved accuracies
83 in Sweden, with volume RMSE reduced from 37.9% to 30.2% in boreal forests (Persson et al., 2021).
84 However, a recurring limitation is, for instance, a saturation effect in timber volume predictions—
85 particularly above 300 m³/ha (Santoro et al., 2011) —which contributes to lower overall accuracy

86 compared to models based on airborne laser scanning (ALS) data (Wittke et al., 2019). Recent advances
87 in Deep Learning (DL) show promise for improving EO-based forest resource mapping. Ge et al. (2023a)
88 demonstrated that the prediction of Lorey's height using Sentinel-2 data alone, as well as combined
89 Sentinel-2 and SAR data, improved by 0.3% to 1.6% RMSE when applying the UNet DL method
90 compared to traditional approaches such as kNN, random forest, or linear regression. Similarly, Astola
91 et al. (2021) reported RMSE improvements of 7.9% for volume and 2.5% for height when using DL
92 models compared to reference methods. Nevertheless, DL remains underutilized in regression tasks for
93 EO-based forest attribute estimation, especially when compared to its more widespread application in
94 classification tasks such as disturbance mapping (Yuan et al., 2020).

95 One of the key challenges in applying DL to forest resource mapping is the limited availability and
96 quality of suitable training data (Ball et al., 2017; Li et al., 2019). NFI datasets are often considered weak
97 labels in the context of DL because they lack spatial context due to a relatively small plot size. To address
98 this challenge, transfer learning has emerged as a promising strategy in various remote sensing tasks
99 e.g. (Wurm et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2023; Kuzu et al., 2024), but only a few studies have been used for
100 in the context of forest resource mapping (Astola et al., 2021; Ge et al., 2023a). Instead of training a
101 model solely on data from the target region, transfer learning allows the use of a pre-trained model—
102 developed on a related task —which can then be fine-tuned using a smaller set of local training data.
103 This approach leverages the generalizable features learned during pre-training, enabling effective
104 model adaptation even with limited labelled data. In addition, ALS-based forest resource maps can
105 offer high-quality, wall-to-wall training data that can complement or substitute traditional plot-based
106 labels (Ge et al., 2022, 2023a). For example, Ge et al. (2023a) demonstrated the successful training of
107 models in Finnish Lapland using ALS-derived maps, along with optical and SAR satellite imagery,
108 followed by fine-tuning with plot-level measurement data in southern Finland. To further evaluate the
109 effectiveness of this approach, applying transfer learning to neighbouring countries—such as Norway—
110 provides an ideal test case.

111 In this study, we develop and evaluate the potential of UNet-based deep learning models in multiple
112 EO data combinations to estimate timber volume and Lorey's height using optical (Sentinel-2) and SAR
113 (Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2) satellite imagery. ALS-based forest resource maps serve as wall-to-wall
114 training data for models trained in both Finland and Norway. We investigate transfer learning by fine-
115 tuning ALS-based pre-trained models with Norwegian NFI plots, both by transferring the Finnish model
116 to Norwegian conditions and exploring further options for improving the Norwegian model. The
117 performance and uncertainty of the UNet models trained on existing forest resource maps are
118 compared with kNN models trained on NFI field plots. Model uncertainty is assessed using both a test
119 dataset of NFI plots, which was not used in modelling, and an independent validation dataset of forest
120 stands. Our research questions are: (1) Which modelling method -- UNet or kNN -- achieves the highest
121 accuracy? (2) Can transfer learning, where NFI field plots are incorporated in the model, improve the
122 UNet accuracy, especially in the case of applying the Finnish model to Norwegian conditions? (3) Can
123 the inclusion of SAR imagery enhance the model's prediction accuracy?

124 2. Materials and Methods

125 The overall workflow developed for this study (Fig. 1) consists of four main processing steps: (a) kNN
126 modelling; (b) pretraining UNet models using ALS-based forest resource maps from Finland and
127 Norway; (c) fine-tuning UNet models from Finland and Norway for the Norwegian study site; and (d)

128 assessing the uncertainty associated with each model type (k-NN, pretrained UNet, and finetuned
 129 UNet).

130

131 *Figure 1. Overview of the workflow used for assessing the accuracy of different models (kNN, UNet, finetuned UNet). The*
 132 *input datasets are marked with rectangles (satellite imagery data, forest resource maps, Norwegian NFI plots, and*
 133 *Norwegian validation stands), dark grey indicating input for training the models and light green for validation models. The*
 134 *intermediate models (kNN, UNet, and finetuned UNet) are marked with a snipped rectangle. The main processing steps*
 135 *are shown with rounded rectangles (a-d corresponding to the main text). V is volume, and H is Lorey's height, S2 is Sentinel-2*
 136 *optical images, S1 is Sentinel-1 SAR images, and P2 is PALSAR-2 SAR images. FI = Finland and NO = Norway.*

137 2.1. Datasets

138 2.1.1. Satellite imagery data and pre-processing

139 ESA Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellites operating with the Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) provide optical
 140 imagery data on 13 spectral bands at a 2–3-day revisit frequency in the Nordic countries, in visible,
 141 near-infrared, and the short-wave infrared part of the electromagnetic spectrum. In this study, we used
 142 the Level-2 surface reflectance products provided by ESA at the visible and near infrared bands (B2, B3,
 143 B4, B5, B8) and short-wave infrared bands (B11, B12). The 20 m resolution bands (B5, B11, B12) were
 144 resampled into 10 m resolution using the bilinear interpolation method for matching the resolution
 145 with the other bands (10 m). The Sentinel-2 data were further processed with the Terramonitor
 146 compositing script (Miettinen et al., 2021), producing growing season composites by weighting based
 147 on cloudiness, haze, and shadows. The compositing process also delivered a quality flag that was used
 148 for filtering cloud-affected or bad-quality pixels.

149 In this study, we have used two types of SAR datasets. The first consisted of C-band backscatter imagery
 150 acquired by Sentinel-1A in Interferometric Wide (IW) swath mode, using VV and VH polarisation. The
 151 images in Ground-Range-Detected (GRD) format were pre-processed using the GAMMA Remote
 152 Sensing software (Werner et al., 2000), which resulted in geocoded and radiometric terrain corrected
 153 g0 backscatter images. The images were subsequently resampled to 10 m to match the Sentinel-2
 154 imagery. The Sentinel-1 data acquired within a year (30 to 31 images) were then used to calculate the

155 annual mean backscatter per polarization. Maps depicting areas of layover or shadow were applied to
156 mask such areas.

157 The second type of SAR dataset was based on the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA), which
158 releases free and open annual mosaics of the L-band data acquired by the Phased-Array type L-band
159 SAR (PALSAR-2) onboard the Advanced Land Observing Satellite-2 (ALOS-2). The backscatter mosaics,
160 with a resolution of $\sim 25 \times 25 \text{ m}^2$, are produced from imagery acquired in Fine Beam Dual Polarization
161 mode (HH and HV), using stripmap mode under JAXA's global basic observation scenario. The images
162 used to generate the mosaics were radiometric terrain-corrected, and geocoded to a geographic spatial
163 reference system, as with (Shimada and Ohtaki, 2010). In this study, the HH and HV mosaics were
164 resampled to a 10 m grid and masked for layover and shadow using the layover/shadow maps produced
165 by JAXA.

166 All satellite imagery datasets were processed for the study areas in Finland and Norway. In Finland, the
167 datasets were processed for the year 2020, and in Norway for 2021, to align as closely as possible with
168 the timing of the ALS-based forest resource maps.

169 2.1.2. Finnish reference datasets

170 The Finnish UNet model was trained based on the wall-to-wall Finnish ALS-based forest resource map
171 produced by the Finnish Forest Centre using ALS acquisitions from 2020 and associated field inventory
172 plots as training for k-NN based approaches (Maltamo and Packalen, 2014). The map covers the core
173 central and southern regions of Finland (Fig. 2), capturing boreal forests in 16 m spatial resolution. The
174 study area has relatively small elevation differences, with the highest points generally less than 300 m
175 above sea level. The forest in the reference areas has around 40% pine, more than 30% spruce, and the
176 rest deciduous trees. The average forest volume across the study sites was $120 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$, with an average
177 height of 14 m.

178 2.1.3. Norwegian reference datasets

179 The Norwegian study site covers approximately 210,000 km^2 of land, encompassing the South-Eastern,
180 Central, Southern, and Western regions, extending from the county of Trøndelag and south (Fig. 2). It
181 is located in the boreal climate zone and contains most of the productive forest of Norway. The boreal
182 forests are dominated by three main species: Norway spruce, Scots pine, and deciduous trees, primarily

183 birch, which are often mixed with coniferous species. The study site has a diverse topographical
 184 variation.

185
 186 *Figure 2 The Norwegian study area (highlighted in green on the Nordic map) is where the different model types—kNN, UNet,*
 187 *and UNet fine-tuned —were evaluated. Green dots represent the NFI plots used for testing, while pink coloured dots indicate*
 188 *the training NFI plots used for the kNN model and UNet fine-tuning. Brown areas mark the independent validation stands.*
 189 *Panel A shows a zoomed-in view of the study area, with panels B and C highlighting two example validation stands used in*
 190 *the accuracy assessment. The background maps are the ALS-based timber volume map from Kilden (NIBIO, 2025) and*
 191 *Google satellite imagery in panel A.*

192 Different field observation datasets were utilized in this study (Fig.2, Table 1). First, the Norwegian NFI
 193 is a continuously operating inventory based on a permanent sample grid, where each field plot is
 194 remeasured every five years (Breidenbach et al., 2020). The NFI field measurements are carried out
 195 within circular 250 m² plots where the diameter at breast height (dbh) and species of all trees with a
 196 dbh >= 5 cm are recorded, and the height of ten trees is measured to calculate timber volume and
 197 Lorey's height. Only NFI plots measured in 2021 within a valid remote sensing-based forest mask were
 198 included in the study, which resulted in 1566 NFI plots. 541 NFI plots were set aside for testing and not
 199 used for kNN or DL modelling, and the remaining 1025 NFI plots were used in model training (Table 1).

200 Additional stand-level field measurements (Fig. 2, Table 1), independent of the NFI, were used for
 201 validation (Koma and Breidenbach, 2025). The dataset includes two subsets: (a) mature stands in Asker
 202 (eastern region) and Alver (western region), where 10–15 plots per stand were sampled following NFI
 203 protocols. Mean timber volume and Lorey's height were calculated to characterise each stand. (b) Long-
 204 term field trials assessing forest management methods, consisting of 1–30 adjacent rectangular stands.
 205 Within each stand, dbh and species were recorded for all trees, and height was measured for every
 206 fourth tree. Stand-level timber volume and Lorey's height were calculated and aggregated to trial-level
 207 averages. After applying a remote sensing-based forest mask and excluding cloud-covered stands from
 208 2021, 44 validation stands covering 62 ha were available for uncertainty assessment.

209 *Table 1 Summary statistics of training NFI, testing NFI, and validation stand datasets. The table includes the number of*
 210 *observations (N), minimum (Min), maximum (Max), mean, and standard deviation (SD) for each variable (Volume, Lorey's*
 211 *height, area of the plot, and the stands).*

Dataset	Variable	Unit	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Training NFI plots	Volume	m ³ ha ⁻¹	1025	0.18	1157.59	118.13	127.99
	Lorey's height	m		2.40	28.18	11.96	5.11

	Area	m ²		250			
Testing NFI plots	Volume	m ³ ha ⁻¹	541	0.30	779.70	125.91	118.66
	Lorey's height	m		3.40	28.00	12.38	4.66
	Area	m ²		250			
Validation stands	Volume	m ³ ha ⁻¹	44	100.62	906.70	369.14	206.17
	Lorey's height	m		12.24	26.55	18.58	4.11
	Area	ha		0.11	4.32	1.40	1.06

212

213 Third, the Norwegian Forest Resource Map (SR16) was used as a wall-to-wall training dataset for the
 214 UNet model. These spatially continuous maps provide estimates of timber volume, Lorey's height, and
 215 other forest attributes at a 16 m × 16 m resolution and are operationally updated each year following
 216 the workflow described by Hauglin et al. (2021). They are produced by combining NFI plot data with
 217 predictor variables derived from nationwide ALS acquisitions conducted by the Norwegian Mapping
 218 Agency. Species-specific univariate linear mixed-effects regression models are used to account for
 219 systematic differences across ALS projects and regions. To ensure consistency, NFI plot values are
 220 projected to a common reference date, and a remote sensing-based forest mask is applied.

221 2.2. Modelling

222 2.2.1. kNN modeling

223 The kNN method has been chosen as the baseline method to be compared with the DL method, since
 224 it has been successfully applied in estimating forest variables and it is operationally used, for example,
 225 in Finland (McRoberts and Tomppo, 2007). It is a non-parametric algorithm, where the predictions of
 226 the target variables are obtained from as the averages of the k neighbours with the smallest distances
 227 to the target unit in the auxiliary space. The kNN model can be described as follows:

$$228 \hat{y}_p = \sum_{i \in I} w_{i,p} y_i$$

229 where the predicted vector for each pixel is \hat{y}_p , y_i is the vector of observations for the i -th contributing
 230 unit in the reference set, I is the subset of contributing units that are nearest with respect to the
 231 distance metric, and $w_{i,p}$ is the weight of i -th contributing unit calculated as

$$232 w_{i,p} = \begin{cases} \frac{d_{i,p}^{-t}}{\sum_{i \in I} d_{i,p}^{-t}} & i \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

233 where $t > 0$ weight units inversely to their feature space distance or distance squared from pixel p . -
 234 In this study, $t = 1$ was used, with Euclidean distance and seven nearest neighbours ($k=7$).

235 The kNN training database was constructed by intersecting training NFI plot locations (Fig.2, Table 1)
 236 with the pre-processed EO datasets, including Sentinel-2, Sentinel-1, and PALSAR-2 bands. For each
 237 plot, all pixels overlapping the 250 m² plot area were considered, and their contributions were
 238 weighted by the fraction of pixel area falling within the plot. A weighted mean of the intersecting pixel
 239 values was then computed, resulting in a training table that combined field-measured attributes with
 240 corresponding EO features. Predictions were generated for each test NFI plot and validation stand
 241 locations.

242 2.2.2. UNet model

243 A variant of a UNet model (Ronneberger et al., 2015) has been adapted for this study, which is a
 244 convolutional neural network (CNN) widely used in biomedical image and other semantic segmentation
 245 tasks. Compared to a basic CNN, UNet models allow extraction of deeper feature representations from
 246 the input image datasets and keep the feature map size unchanged, which makes it suitable for pixel-
 247 level regression tasks.

248 The UNet architecture applied (Fig.3.) in this study is a symmetric encoder–decoder network designed
 249 for pixel-level predictions. The encoder contains a double-convolution structure, which includes a 2D
 250 convolution, batch normalization, and ReLU activation. At each step, 2x2 max-pooling halves the
 251 feature map. This allows the model to gradually transition from capturing fine, local details to learning
 252 more global spatial patterns. The decoder mirrors this process by restoring the original resolution
 253 through upsampling operations. To recover information lost during downsampling, skip connections
 254 link corresponding encoder and decoder layers, as the pooling operation discarded some details.
 255 Applying skip-connection, the shallow feature maps are concatenated to deep features recovered from
 256 up-sampling. Finally, a 1x1 convolution projects the restored feature map into the target space,
 257 producing the desired pixel-wise predictions without altering the spatial dimensions.

258

259

260 *Figure 3 The UNet model architecture used in the study. Each box represents a feature map with its size indicated nearby.*

261 2.2.3. UNet model training

262 First, all input datasets were prepared for training the UNet model (Fig. 4). During pre-training, the
 263 Finnish and Norwegian wall-to-wall ALS-based forest resource maps, described in Sections 2.1.2–2.1.3,
 264 were used as reference datasets. The pre-training dataset comprised 1,068 rectangular patches for
 265 Finland and 1,025 patches for Norway, each with a size of 2.56 × 2.56 km² (256 × 256 pixels). These
 266 patches were randomly distributed across the forested areas covered by the ALS-based forest resource
 267 maps. The resolution of the forest resource maps was aligned with the satellite imagery datasets by
 268 resampling the native spatial resolution of 16 × 16 m to 10 × 10 m. For fine-tuning, 1,025 Norwegian
 269 NFI plots selected for training were used. When preparing image patches related to the training NFI

270 plots, only the 10 × 10 m pixels intersecting the field plot locations contained valid values; all other
271 pixels were masked out (set to no-data).

272 Predictor variables were extracted for the selected image patches (for both pre-training and fine-
273 tuning) based on the pre-processed and filtered EO bands from Sentinel-2 only (S2), and from the
274 multisource Sentinel-2, Sentinel-1, and PALSAR-2 datasets (S2S1P2), as described in Section 2.1.1. For
275 independent validation, EO image patches related to the NFI test set—which included 541 field plots
276 set aside at the beginning of the modelling process—and validation stands were prepared using the
277 same patch size, containing the relevant plots and stands. Within all image patches, non-forest pixels
278 were masked out. All EO patches were further normalised on a per-band basis using z-score
279 normalization, where each band’s mean was subtracted and the result divided by its standard
280 deviation.

281

282 *Figure 4 Overview of the UNet model training workflow. Input patches are prepared for the Finnish and Norwegian datasets.*
283 *An independent test NFI plots were set aside before model training and used only for final uncertainty assessment. During*
284 *UNet pre-training and fine-tuning, the forest resource maps and training NFI plots used were randomly split 10 times into*
285 *training, validation and test subsets. The internal validation and test are used solely to run the DL model and are not used for*
286 *uncertainty assessment in this study.*

287 During UNet model pre-training, the overall datasets were randomly split into training (70%), validation
288 (15%), and testing (15%) patches. The Adam optimiser was used with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-4} .
289 A ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler was applied to adaptively reduce the learning rate by half when the
290 validation loss plateaued, with a patience of ten epochs. The model was trained for 200 epochs with a
291 mild weight decay of 1×10^{-5} . The best-performing model was selected based on the lowest validation
292 loss, determined using the internal validation data, and the corresponding weights were saved for
293 subsequent fine-tuning for each target variable. Training was conducted with a batch size of 16. The
294 final model was used to predict EO patches corresponding to the test NFI plot locations and validation
295 stands.

296 For UNet fine-tuning, the pre-trained models from Finland and Norway were used as input. The UNet
 297 model was reinitialised with the pre-trained weights. The fine-tuning dataset, based on prepared
 298 patches for the training NFI plot locations, was randomly split into 75% for training 24% for validation,
 299 and 1% for testing. During fine-tuning, the pre-trained weights were frozen. The learning rate was set
 300 to 1×10^{-6} , the number of epochs to 30, and the batch size to 16. This fine-tuning procedure was
 301 repeated ten times, each with a different random split of the training dataset. The best-performing
 302 fine-tuned model, based on validation loss, was used to predict volume and Lorey's height values for
 303 the NFI and stand-level validation datasets.

304 2.3. Uncertainty assessment

305 Uncertainty assessment was carried out using a set-aside group of test NFI plots - which were never
 306 used during modelling - along with independent validation stands. The uncertainty was evaluated
 307 separately for the test NFI plot and for validation stands using weighted root mean square error (RMSE)
 308 and weighted BIAS, which was calculated as

$$309 \quad \{RMSE, bias\} = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^\varphi \right]^\omega$$

310 with $\varphi = 2$ and $\omega = 0.5$ for RMSE and $\varphi = 1$ and $\omega = 1$ for bias, where y_i and \hat{y}_i represent the observed and
 311 estimated forest attributes at the stand level, and w_i is the area of each NFI plot and validation stand; i
 312 $= 1, \dots, n$.

313 We further calculated the weighted coefficient of determination (R^2) as:

$$314 \quad R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

315 where \bar{y} is the mean of the observed values.

316 3. Results

317 Prediction uncertainties were assessed for the different types of models (kNN, UNet, fine-tuned UNet)
 318 using only optical and SAR-based imagery data as predictors. Furthermore, the UNet model was trained
 319 on Finnish and Norwegian forest resource maps, and the effect of fine-tuning was evaluated. The
 320 results are presented separately for timber volume and Lorey's height.

321 3.1. Timber volume

322 Across all cases, UNet models originating from the Norwegian forest resource map—both the base and
 323 fine-tuned variants—consistently outperformed kNN (Table 2, Fig.5, Table S1). Compared to kNN, RMSE
 324 was reduced by up to 16.6% for NFI plots and 12.1% for stands, with corresponding R^2 increases of 0.24
 325 and 0.27. Bias reductions were also notable, reaching 8% for NFI plots and 20.4% for stands. In contrast,
 326 the UNet model based on the Finnish ALS-based forest resource map showed only marginal or no
 327 improvements over kNN. For NFI plots, the Finnish UNet reduced RMSE by just 2% and improved R^2 by
 328 0.03. For stands, however, kNN outperformed the Finnish UNet, lowering RMSE by 3.9% and increasing
 329 R^2 by 0.1. Regarding bias, the Finnish UNet achieved a 3% reduction for NFI plots, while kNN showed a
 330 1.2% lower bias than the fine-tuned Finnish UNet for stands.

331 Fine-tuning effects were most beneficial in UNet models using the Finnish ALS-based forest resource
 332 map (Table 2, Fig. 5). For these models improvements ranged from 0.1% to 4.3% for RMSE, 0.02 to 0.13
 333 for R^2 , and 1.1% to 5.9% for bias. In contrast, fine-tuning the Norwegian forest resource map-based

334 models (Table 2, Fig. 5) yielded limited gains for NFI plots when using S2S1P2 predictors, with
 335 improvements of 0.6% in RMSE, 0.01 in R², and 5.4% in bias. No improvement was observed when
 336 using S2-only predictors. At the stand level, fine-tuning the Norwegian forest resource map-based
 337 model often led to reduced model performance, with RMSE increasing by 0.2% to 1.2%, R² decreasing
 338 by 0.01 to 0.02, and underestimation (bias) increasing by 0.3% to 6.1%.

339 Combining optical and SAR predictors generally enhanced UNet performance compared to using
 340 Sentinel-2 data alone (Table 2, Fig. 5). For the best-performing UNet model, switching from S2 to
 341 S2S1P2 predictors reduced RMSE by 4.2% for NFI plots and 2.7% for stands, while R² increased by 0.05
 342 for both validation types. In terms of bias, compared to the S2-only model, the S2S1P2 model showed
 343 improvements ranging from 0.6% to 5.4% for NFI plots and 13.2% to 13.9% for stands. For kNN, the
 344 impact of adding SAR data was less consistent: RMSE for NFI plots decreased by 1% and R² increased
 345 by 0.02, but RMSE rose by 2.7% and R² declined by 0.07 for stands. Bias was reduced with S2S1P2, by
 346 2.4% for NFI plots and 0.1% for stands.

347 *Table 2 Overall uncertainty assessment for timber volume comparing kNN, UNet, and fine-tuned UNet models trained on*
 348 *Finnish (FI) and Norwegian (NO) data. Results are shown for NFI plots, validation stands, and two types of predictor variable*
 349 *combinations (Pred. type): S2 (Sentinel-2) and S2S1P2 (Sentinel-2 with Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2). Fine-tuned models were*
 350 *pre-trained on ALS-based forest resource maps from Finland (FI) or Norway (NO) and fine-tuned further using Norwegian*
 351 *training NFI plots.*

Test data type	Pred. type	Training data	kNN	UNet	Fine-tuned UNet	kNN	UNet	Fine-tuned UNet	kNN	UNet	Fine-tuned UNet
			RMSE [%]			BIAS [%]			R ²		
NFI	S2	FI		74.5	72.6		-16.2	-7.9		0.37	0.41
NFI	S2	NO	74.7	61.3	61.3	7.9	2.5	2.1	0.37	0.58	0.58
NFI	S2S1P2	FI		71.8	71.7		-4.1	-2.5		0.42	0.42
NFI	S2S1P2	NO	73.7	57.7	57.1	5.5	8.1	2.7	0.39	0.62	0.63
Stand	S2	FI		62.0	57.7		-38.1	-32.2		0.04	0.17
Stand	S2	NO	48.5	41.8	42.0	-22.0	-14.7	-15	0.42	0.57	0.56
Stand	S2S1P2	FI		55.7	55.1		-24.2	-23.1		0.23	0.25
Stand	S2S1P2	NO	51.2	39.1	40.3	-21.9	-1.5	-7.6	0.35	0.62	0.60

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354 *Figure 5 Observed vs. predicted timber volume for different predictor types: S2 (Sentinel-2 only) and S2S1P2 (Sentinel-2 with*
 355 *Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2). Models include kNN, UNet, and fine-tuned UNet trained on Finnish (FI) or Norwegian (NO)*
 356 *datasets. Fine-tuned models were first pre-trained on ALS-based forest resource maps (FI or NO) and then updated using*
 357 *Norwegian NFI training plots.*

358 3.2. Lorey's height

359 Similarly to volume, UNet models outperformed kNN in all cases (Table 3, Fig.6, Table S2). RMSE
 360 improvements ranged from 3.4% to 4.6% for NFI plots and 3.7 % to 4.4% for stands, and R^2 increases

361 with 0.14 and 0.18 for NFI plots and to 0.26 to 0.31 for stands. Bias reductions varied between 1.1%
 362 and 1.3% for NFI plots and 8.3% and 9.5% for stands.

363 The effects of fine-tuning followed a similar overall pattern to those observed for volume. RMSE
 364 improvements (Table 3, Fig. 6) ranged from 0.3% to 7.5%, while R^2 changes varied from 0.01 to 0.46.
 365 The most substantial gains were achieved by fine-tuning the pre-trained Finnish model with Norwegian
 366 NFI plot data, where R^2 increased from 0.03 to 0.38 and from -0.17 to 0.29, in the case of NFI plots and
 367 validation stands, respectively. However, when RMSE improvements for NFI plots were small ($<1\%$), the
 368 stand-level results showed less consistency, including instances of worsening performance with fine-
 369 tuning—evidenced by increased RMSE and decreased R^2 (Table 3, Fig. 6).

370 Similar to volume, combining optical and SAR predictors led to improvement in UNet performance for
 371 Lorey’s height estimation on NFI plots (Table 3, Fig. 6), reducing RMSE by 1.1% and increasing R^2 by
 372 0.04. However, for stand-level predictions, RMSE increased by 0.6% and R^2 decreased by 0.04,
 373 indicating that S2-only predictors can achieve comparable accuracy. Regarding bias, S2-only predictors
 374 yielded a 0.1% improvement for NFI plots, while the S2S1P2 combination reduced stand-level bias by
 375 0.3%. For kNN, differences between S2 and S2S1P2 were minimal: RMSE changed by 0.1% and R^2
 376 remained unchanged for NFI plots, while RMSE decreased by 0.1% and R^2 increased by 0.01 for stands.
 377 Bias was slightly reduced using combined optical and SAR predictors—by 0.1% for NFI plots and 0.9%
 378 for stands.

379 *Table 3 Overall uncertainty assessment for Lorey’s height comparing kNN, UNet, and fine-tuned UNet models trained on*
 380 *Finnish (FI) and Norwegian (NO) data. Results are shown for NFI plots, validation stands, and two types of predictor variable*
 381 *combinations (Pred. type): S2 (Sentinel-2) and S2S1P2 (Sentinel-2 with Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2). Fine-tuned models were*
 382 *pre-trained on ALS-based forest resource maps from Finland (FI) or Norway (NO) and fine-tuned further using Norwegian*
 383 *training NFI plots.*

Test data type	Pred. type	Training data	kNN	UNet	Fine-Tuned UNet	kNN	UNet	Fine-Tuned UNet	kNN	UNet	Fine-Tuned UNet
			RMSE [%]			BIAS [%]			R^2		
NFI	S2	FI		30.2	29.6		2.5	-1.7		0.36	0.38
NFI	S2	NO	29.8	26.7	26.4	2.7	4.2	1.4	0.37	0.50	0.51
NFI	S2S1P2	FI		37.1	29.6		6.1	3.5		0.03	0.38
NFI	S2S1P2	NO	29.9	25.8	25.3	2.6	5.0	1.5	0.37	0.53	0.55
Stand	S2	FI		16.6	17.0		0.8	-3.2		0.48	0.46
Stand	S2	NO	21.0	17.9	18.5	-8.7	-2.8	-5.2	0.17	0.40	0.36
Stand	S2S1P2	FI		24.9	19.4		15.7	3.3		-0.17	0.29
Stand	S2S1P2	NO	20.9	17.2	17.5	-7.8	0.5	-2.6	0.18	0.44	0.43

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386 *Figure 6 Observed vs. predicted Lorey's height for different predictor types: S2 (Sentinel-2 only) and S2S1P2 (Sentinel-2 with*
 387 *Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2). Models include kNN, UNet, and fine-tuned UNet trained on Finnish (FI) or Norwegian (NO)*
 388 *datasets. Fine-tuned models were first pre-trained on ALS-based forest resource maps (FI or NO) and then updated using*
 389 *Norwegian NFI training plots.*

390 4. Discussion

391 We evaluated the uncertainties of kNN, UNet, and fine-tuned UNet models for estimating forest
 392 volume and Lorey's height distributed across a large part of Norway using a total of 76 ha area. This

393 study provides an evaluation of Sentinel-2 and SAR imagery using yearly composites for large-scale
394 forest resource mapping in Norway, where earlier efforts have relied mainly on Landsat data (Gjertsen,
395 2007), and current operational mapping of volume and Lorey's height is based exclusively on ALS
396 predictors (Hauglin et al., 2021). The best overall accuracies ranged from 39.1 to 57.1 % RMSE for
397 volume and 16.6 to 25.3 % RMSE for Lorey's height in the case of two different validation datasets.
398 These results were comparable with other studies using only satellite-based imagery datasets from a
399 single time in the boreal forest region, RMSE ranging from 27.2 to 59.3 % for volume and 15.4 to 33.5%
400 for Lorey's height (Wittke et al., 2019; Persson et al., 2021; Miettinen et al., 2021; Ge et al., 2022,
401 2023a).

402 The UNet models trained on wall-to-wall forest resource maps—particularly those derived from
403 Norwegian ALS data—consistently outperformed kNN, underscoring the advantages of applying deep
404 learning to satellite-based forest attribute mapping (Tables 2–3). The effective use of ALS-based forest
405 resource maps as training data for deep learning has been confirmed by a few previous studies (Becker
406 et al., 2023; Ge et al., 2022, 2023a). Astola et al. (2021) demonstrated that using a 3×3 window around
407 the plot with a deep learning method improved accuracy compared to a pixel-wise approach,
408 supporting our finding that spatial contextual information enhances deep learning training. In contrast
409 to earlier studies, our work evaluated cross-country transferability using independent validation
410 datasets distributed across a large spatial scale. In case of achieved accuracies, similar patterns have
411 been reported in other DL-based boreal forest studies. For example, Ge et al. (2022) demonstrated
412 improvements in Lorey's height prediction in Finland, with RMSE decreasing from 30.1% to 24.1% at
413 the plot level and from 19.7% to 15.4% at the stand level when moving from gradient boosting to UNet-
414 based deep learning. Astola et al. (2021) reported that deep learning reduced RMSE from 50.3% to
415 42.4% for volume and from 30.7% to 28.2% for height when using plots as validation data. In their case,
416 only the best-performing DL model was compared against Random Forest, which included an ALS-
417 derived canopy height model as a predictor. In comparison, the improvements we observed were of
418 similar or greater magnitude, with volume RMSE reduced from 73.7% to 57.1% and Lorey's height from
419 29.9% to 25.3%. Our results further provide a more comprehensive assessment of bias by considering
420 two types of validation datasets. For NFI plots (<200 m³ ha⁻¹), UNet reduced overestimation, consistent
421 with the findings of Astola et al. (2021) and Ge et al. (2022, 2023a). However, these earlier studies did
422 not analyze bias patterns, also including high-volume forests (>200 m³ ha⁻¹), where we found that UNet
423 reduced underestimation and was less biased compared to kNN.

424 Our study also examined the geographical transferability of pre-trained models from Finland to
425 Norwegian conditions. Cross-country transfer is rarely explored; most previous research has focused
426 on transfers within Finland (Astola et al., 2021; Ge et al., 2023a), while Lang et al. (2019) demonstrated
427 that the same DL methods could be applied across countries to map vegetation height in Switzerland
428 and Gabon. Our results show that Finnish pre-trained UNet models, when fine-tuned with Norwegian
429 NFI plots, achieved accuracies comparable to or exceeding those of kNN models (Tables 2–3). This is
430 consistent with Astola et al. (2021), who that transfer learning yielded equal or better performance,
431 and with Ge et al. (2023a), who showed that fine-tuning improved accuracy relative to models applied
432 without adaptation. Astola et al. (2021) also demonstrated that frozen pre-trained networks facilitated
433 model transfer, which is in line with our findings. At the same time, models trained directly on
434 Norwegian data achieved higher accuracies than fine-tuned Finnish models, consistent with results
435 from other deep learning-based studies (Kattenborn et al., 2021). By explicitly evaluating performance,
436 including high-volume forest stands (>200 m³ ha⁻¹), we further found that fine-tuning could, in some
437 cases, slightly underperform compared to models without fine-tuning, highlighting a limitation when
438 it is applied to regions with values outside where the model was trained. Nevertheless, the fine-tuning

439 results also showed that in most cases bias was reduced, whereas models without fine-tuning often
440 exhibited higher bias, which aligns with Ge et al., (2023a).

441 Our results indicate that combining optical and SAR predictors generally improved model performance
442 compared to optical-only inputs (Tables 2–3). Similar trends have been reported in other boreal forest
443 studies. For example, Persson et al. (2021) demonstrated that including SAR data reduced the RMSE
444 for volume estimates in Sweden from 37.2% to 30.2%. Likewise, Ge et al. (2022, 2023a) reported an
445 improvement in Lorey’s height prediction in Finland, with RMSE decreasing from 30.3% to 18.1%. In
446 our study, the magnitude of improvement was smaller: the maximum reduction in RMSE was from
447 61.3% to 57.1% for volume and from 26.4% to 25.3% for Lorey’s height. Overall, we also found that the
448 addition of SAR, can improve capturing forest structure, which aligns with several studies (Wittke et al.,
449 2019; Persson et al., 2021; Ge et al., 2022, 2023a). Two main factors can explain the minor
450 improvement in RMSE. First, the more complex topography in Norway compared to Sweden or Finland
451 can influence the SAR backscatter signal quality. Second, Persson et al. (2021) utilized TanDEM-X data,
452 which offers a finer spatial resolution (10 m) and a more frequent acquisition cycle (11-day repeat
453 cycle), and, most importantly, interferometric coherence that is inherently sensitive to vertical
454 structure of forests (Olesk et al., 2016). In contrast, our study also relied on PALSAR-2 data additionally
455 to S1 with coarser resolution (25 m) and used a single annual mosaic.

456 5. Conclusion

457 Our study demonstrates the potential of using spatially continuous ALS-based forest resource maps as
458 training data for UNet-based deep learning models. In contrast to most previous boreal forest mapping
459 approaches—which most commonly rely on end-to-end training using field plots of specified sizes and
460 satellite imagery within a single country—we show that ALS-derived maps can serve as an effective
461 training dataset that also leverages spatial context and can be applied across different Nordic countries.
462 We found that deep learning models outperform kNN method by reducing overestimation in low-
463 volume (<200 m³ ha⁻¹) forests and underestimation in high-volume (>200 m³ ha⁻¹) forests. A key
464 advantage of deep learning is its transferability with a limited set of local field plots. Our results indicate
465 that a model pre-trained on Finnish data performed comparably to kNN trained with Norwegian data.
466 With the development of more comprehensive foundation models trained on multi-country datasets,
467 this approach may enable robust, large-scale, cross-country forest resource mapping.

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474 Author contributions

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477 curation, Writing review and editing, JM: Formal analysis, Project administration, Funding acquisition,
478 Writing review and editing, JB: Project administration, Funding acquisition, Writing review and editing

479 Data and code statement

480 The pre-processed EO dataset is available upon request from the corresponding author. The used
481 methods are available within the Forestry-TEP (<https://f-tep.com/>) developed by VTT.

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592

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594

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596 Appendix

597 *Table S1 Overall uncertainty assessment for timber volume comparing kNN, UNet, and fine-tuned UNet models trained on*
 598 *Finnish (FI) and Norwegian (NO) data. Results are shown for NFI plots, validation stands, and two types of predictor variable*
 599 *combinations (Pred. type): S2 (Sentinel-2) and S2S1P2 (Sentinel-2 with Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2). Fine-tuned models were*
 600 *pre-trained on ALS-based forest resource maps from Finland (FI) or Norway (NO) and fine-tuned further using Norwegian*
 601 *training NFI plots.*

Test data type	Pred. type	Model type	kNN	UNet	Fine-tuned UNet	kNN	UNet	Fine-Tuned UNet	kNN	UNet	Fine-Tuned UNet
			RMSE [m ³ ha ⁻¹]			BIAS [m ³ ha ⁻¹]			R ²		
NFI	S2	FI		93.8	91.4		-20.4	-9.9		0.37	0.41
NFI	S2	NO	94.0	77.2	77.2	9.9	3.1	2.7	0.37	0.58	0.58
NFI	S2S1P2	FI		90.4	90.3		-5.1	-3.1		0.42	0.42
NFI	S2S1P2	NO	92.8	72.6	72.0	7.0	10.2	3.4	0.39	0.62	0.63
Stand	S2	FI		190.1	176.7		-116.6	-98.5		0.04	0.17
Stand	S2	NO	148.6	128.1	128.5	-67.6	-45	-46.0	0.42	0.57	0.56
Stand	S2S1P2	FI		170.6	168.8		-74.2	-70.8		0.23	0.25
Stand	S2S1P2	NO	156.8	119.8	123.5	-67	-4.6	-23.3	0.35	0.62	0.60

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603 *Table S2 Overall uncertainty assessment for Lorey's height comparing kNN, UNet, and fine-tuned UNet models trained on*
 604 *Finnish (FI) and Norwegian (NO) data. Results are shown for NFI plots, validation stands, and two types of predictor variable*
 605 *combinations (Pred. type): S2 (Sentinel-2) and S2S1P2 (Sentinel-2 with Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2). Fine-tuned models were*
 606 *pre-trained on ALS-based forest resource maps from Finland (FI) or Norway (NO) and fine-tuned further using Norwegian*
 607 *training NFI plots.*

Test data type	Pred. type	Model type	kNN	UNet	Fine-Tuned UNet	kNN	UNet	Fine-Tuned UNet	kNN	UNet	Fine-Tuned UNet
			RMSE [m]			BIAS [m]			R ²		
NFI	S2	FI		37.3	36.6		3.0	-2.0		0.36	0.38
NFI	S2	NO	36.9	33.0	32.6	3.4	5.2	1.7	0.37	0.50	0.51
NFI	S2S1P2	FI		45.9	36.7		7.5	4.3		0.03	0.38
NFI	S2S1P2	NO	37.0	31.9	31.3	3.2	6.2	1.8	0.37	0.53	0.55
Stand	S2	FI		28.9	29.7		1.4	-5.6		0.48	0.46
Stand	S2	NO	36.8	31.2	32.3	-15.1	-4.8	-9.2	0.17	0.40	0.36
Stand	S2S1P2	FI		43.6	33.8		27.4	5.7		-0.17	0.29
Stand	S2S1P2	NO	36.5	30.0	30.5	-13.7	0.8	-4.6	0.18	0.44	0.43

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